

**8. INTERNATIONAL
MEDITERRANEAN
SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH
AND INNOVATION CONGRESS
22-23 August 2025
ANTALYA**

EDITORS:

**Prof. Dr. Aliye ÇİLAN AKIN
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Dilshoda MUBARAKOVA
Assist. Prof. Dr. Abdülazim İBRAHİM**

www.isarconference.org

IKSAD
Publishing House

CONGRESS BOOK

INDEX

CONGRES ID		II-IV
PROGRAM		V-XXI
GALLERY		XXII-XXVI
ACADEMIC INCENTIVE		XXVII
NOTIFICATIONS		XXVIII-XXXIV

ISBN: ' 978-625-378-300-6 '

THE IMPACT OF UNCOLLECTIBLE ACCOUNTS AND ACCOUNT RECEIVABLES TURNOVER ON PROFITABILITY IN CONSUMER GOODS FIRMS

DARIYANTI

International Scholar, Gujarat University

ORCID ID: 0009-0008-8854-6177

Ebrahim MOHAMMED

International Scholar, Gujarat University

ORCID ID: 0009-0006-5457-3025

ADRIAN

Lecturer, Stie Jayakarta

Dorton SIBURIAN

International Scholar, Stie Jayakarta

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study to analyze the effect to uncollectible accounts and account receivables turnover on profitability in consumer goods firms listed on the Indonesian Stock Exchange (Period of 2018 – 2020). The method used in the selection of the sample is non-probability through the means of purposive sampling. The population present in this study are consumer goods companies. There are 36 financial statements that are used as samples for this study. The data used in this study is secondary data which are retrieved from the Indonesian Stock Exchange. The result of this study: Partially (t-test) it is known that uncollectible accounts and account receivables turnover have no significant effect on profitability, and the F-test both variables uncollectible accounts and account receivables turnover simultaneously have no effect on profitability. But on the coefficient of determination by 7,9%, while the remaining 92,1% is influenced by other variables that are not included in the variables for this particular study.

Keywords: Uncollectible Accounts, Accounts receivables turnover, Profitability

INTRODUCTION

A company is considered advanced and growing if it is able to sustain its business activities and experience an increase in assets as well as business growth in each period. Such a condition can be achieved if the company is able to manage its operations properly. One of the primary objectives of any company is to generate sustainable income with a positive growth trajectory. To achieve this goal, assets are required. One category of company assets is accounts receivable. accounts receivable tend to exceed accounts payable in most sectors, the retail sector is a notable exception; this is most likely due to the proximity to end-consumers (Daniel et al, 2013). In order to minimize risk, accounts receivable require careful attention and management. Effective receivables management is essential for the company's operational needs, as it can help minimize the occurrence of uncollectible accounts.

Moreover, accounts receivable can also serve as a measure of the company's ability to generate profits from the overall funds or capital invested in the assets used for operations (Hery, 2019). To assess credit risk, management must consider various factors that determine the criteria for evaluating credit risk. Efficient and effective credit management can lead to a high receivable turnover. The higher the turnover of receivables in a company, the better its receivables management. Conversely, lower receivables turnover indicates that a higher amount of working capital is needed to finance the company's receivables. The objective of credit management is not merely to minimize uncollectable account but rather to maximize profits.

Consumer goods companies are businesses that produce and/or distribute goods that are highly needed by society. As a result, sales turnover both cash and credit are relatively high, which indirectly leads to a relatively high amount of uncollectible receivables. A relatively high level of uncollectible receivables combined with a high receivable turnover can affect profits, especially when assessing the effectiveness of the company's assets. Some companies experience fluctuations in uncollectible accounts, receivables turnover, and ROA each year.

There appears to be a contradiction with existing theory, which suggests that when receivables turnover increases, a company's profitability should also increase, and when uncollectible receivables rise, profitability should decrease. From the discussion above, this study aims to examine "The Impact of Uncollectible Accounts and Receivables Turnover on Profitability in Consumer Goods Firms".

METHODOLOGY

This study uses a quantitative descriptive and correlational approach. Quantitative research is an investigation of a phenomenon in an organized way by collecting measurable data and performing statistical, mathematical, or computational techniques (Sidik & Denok, 2021). Correlational research describes the relationships among variables. There are three variables in this study: Uncollectible Accounts (X_1), Accounts Receivable Turnover (X_2), and Profitability (Y).

The population comprises consumer goods industry companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange during 2018–2020. This study applies Nonprobability Sampling; thus, every element of the population does not have an equal chance to be selected as a sample. More precisely, purposive sampling is used whereby the researcher chooses the sample based on certain considerations. The criteria used in this study for selecting samples are as follows:

- Consumer goods industry companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange during the period 2018 – 2020.

- Consumer goods industry companies that published financial statements consecutively from 2018 to 2020.
- Consumer goods industry companies that presented financial statements in Indonesian Rupiah (IDR).

The following hypotheses can be formulated to examine whether there is an influence of uncollectible accounts and account receivables turnover on profitability:

- Ha₁: There is a partial effect of uncollectible accounts on profitability in consumer goods companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange.
- Ha₂: There is a partial effect of account receivables turnover on profitability in consumer goods companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange.
- Ha₃: There is a simultaneous effect of uncollectible accounts and account receivables turnover on profitability in consumer goods companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange.

RESULTS

As the sample was selected based on specific criteria and sampling procedures, 12 companies were selected that met the criteria. The following is the selected sample:

No	Nama of Companies	Code
1	PT. Nippon Indosari Corpindo.Tbk	ROTI
2	PT. Hanjaya Mandala Sampoerna.Tbk	HMSP
3	PT. Indofood Sukses Makmur.Tbk	INDF
4	PT. Indonesia Tobacco.Tbk	ITIC
5	PT. Mulia Boga Raya.Tbk	KEJU
6	PT. Ultra Jaya Milk Industry & Trading.Tbk	ULTJ
7	PT. Kalbe Farma.Tbk	KLBF
8	PT. Mayora Indah.Tbk	MYOR
9	PT. Sekar Laut.Tbk	SKLT
10	PT. Wismilak Inti Makmur.Tbk	WIIM
11	PT. Indofarma.Tbk	INAF
112	PT. Marina Berto.Tbk	MBTO

Table 1: The Samples for Analys

The results of the statistical data processing can be seen in the tables below:

Descriptive Statistics

N		Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
X1 Uncollectible Accounts	36	1.00	122.00	43.44	35.09
X2 Account Receivables Turnover	36	2.00	77.00	14.17	16.89
Y_Profitability	36	-17321.00	53280.00	8602.75	12654.54
Valid N (listwise)	36				

Table 2: Output data processed on SPSS26

- a. It can be seen that uncollectible accounts had a minimum value of 1 in 2018 and 2019, and a maximum value of 122 in 2018. Overall, the average value was 43,44, with a standard deviation of 35,09.
- b. Account Receivables Turnover recorded a minimum value of 2 in 2018, 2019, and 2020, and a maximum value of 77 in 2019. The overall average was 14.17, with a standard deviation of 16,89.
- c. Profitability showed a minimum value of -17321 in 2018, and a maximum value of 53280 in the same year. The overall average value was 8602,75, with a standard deviation of 12654,54.

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Unstandardized Coefficients			Standardized Coefficients
Model	B	Std. Error	Beta
(Constant)	6568.778	4719.265	
X1 Uncollectible Accounts	-16.117	67.654	-.045
X2 Account Receivables Turnover	193.001	140.539	.258

a. Dependent Variable: Y_Profitability

Table 3: Output data processed on SPSS26

Based on the table above, the values used in the multiple linear regression equation are taken from the B (Coefficient) column. The standard form of the multiple linear regression equation is: $Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + e$

Where:

- Constant (α) = 6568,778
- β_1 (X1: Uncollectible Accounts) = -16,117
- β_2 (X2: Account Receivables Turnover) = 193,001
- e = error

Thus, the regression equation shall be expressed as $Y = 6568,778 - 16,117 + 193,001 + \text{error}$

This means a constant value of 6568,778 such that if uncollectable accounts (X_1) and accounts receivable turnover (X_2) equal zero, profitability (Y) will amount to 6568,778.

The uncollectable accounts (X_1) regression coefficient is -16,117, such that if uncollectable accounts increase by 1, profitability (Y) will decrease by approximately 1.611%. A negative coefficient implies the relationship between uncollectable accounts and profitability not being positive or direct.

The account receivables turnover regression coefficient has amounted to 193,001, hence indicating that for every one-time increase in the account receivables turnover, profitability increases by 193,001. Since the coefficient is positive, a direct relationship exists between account receivables turnover and profitability.

Individual Parameter Significance Test (t-Test)

The t-test is used to determine the extent to which each independent variable affects the dependent variable. In this study, the t-test is conducted to examine whether bad debts and receivables turnover individually have a significant effect on profitability.

Unstandardized Coefficients			Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
Model	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	6568.778	4719.265		
	X1_ Uncollectible Accounts	-16.117	67.654	-.045	
	X2_ Accounts Receivables Turnover	193.001	140.539	.258	
				1.392	.173
				-0.238	.813
				1.373	.179

a. **Dependent Variable:** Y_Profitability

Table 4: Output data processed on SPSS26

At a significance level of 0,05 the t-table value is determined to be 1,690.

1. Effect of uncollectable accounts on profitability

The test results show that the calculated t-test for uncollectible accounts is -0,238, which

is less than the t-table value of 1,690. which a significance level below 0,05. Therefore, the null hypothesis (Ho) is accepted, indicating that uncollectable accounts have no significant effect on profitability.

2. Effect of account receivables turnover on profitability

The test results show that the calculated t-test for account receivables turnover is 1,373, which is less than the t-table of 1,690, which a significance lever below 0,05. Therefore, the null hypothesis (Ho) is accepted, indicating that account receivables turnover has no significant effect on profitability.

Simultaneous Test (F-Test)

The simultaneous test is used to determine the combined effect of uncollectible accounts and account receivables turnover on profitability. Based on the F-statistical test, the results are as follows:

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	441906602.17	2	220953301.10	1.41	.258 ^b
	Residual	5162900238.57	33	156451522.38		
	Total	5604806840.75	35			

a. **Dependent Variable:** Y_Profitability

b. **Predictors:** (Constant), X2_ Uncollectible Accounts, X1_ Accounts Receivables Turnover

Table 5: Output data procesed on SPSS26

This test was conducted at a significance level of $\alpha = 0,05$ with the F-table value obtained from the F distribution table being 3,285.

Based on the results of the presented in the table above, to determine the effect of the variables uncollectible accounts (X_1) and account receivables turnover (X_2) on profitability, as measured, the calculated F-test is compared with the F-table. The result shows that F-test less than F-table, namely 1,41 less than 3,285, leading to the conclusion that the null hypothesis (Ho) is accepted. This indicates that, simultaneously, uncollectible accounts and account receivables turnover do not have a significant effect on profitability.

Determination coefficient

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.281 ^a	.079	.023	12508.05830

a. **Predictors:** (Constant), X2_ Uncollectible Accounts, X1_ Accounts Receivabls Turnover

b. **Dependent Variable:** Y_Profitabilitas

Table 6: Output data processed on SPSS26

The results of the coefficient of determination (R^2) indicate that this study has an R-Square value of 0,079 or 7.9%. This means that the independent variables, as a whole have an influence of 7.9% on the dependent variable. The remaining 92,1% is influenced by other factors not included in this study.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of this study, the following conclusions can be follows:

1. Partially, the variable uncollectible accounts have no significant effect on profitability, as indicated by t-test for uncollectible accounts is -0,238, which is less than the t-table value of 1,690.
2. Partially, the variable account receivables turnover also has no significant effect on profitability, as shown by t-test for account receivables turnover is 1,373, which is less than the t-table value of 1,690.
3. The F-test shows that F-test less than F-table, namely 1,412 less than 3,285, This indicates uncollectible accounts and account receivables turnover do not have a significant effect on profitability.
4. The coefficient of determination by 7,9%, while the remaining 92,1% is influenced by other variables that are not included in the variables for this particular study.

The insignificant, during the study period is likely due to the conditions in 2020, which marked the onset of the Covid-19 pandemic. During this time, many firms provided credit relaxation to customers, resulting in delayed receivables that were not immediately recognized as uncollectable. In addition, there was a decline in credit sales due to a shift toward cash sales and advance digital payments. Profitability in this period was also more influenced by external factors such as decreased demand, supply chain disruptions, increased operating cost due to health protocols, and government incentives or assistance that helped prevent a significant decline in profit. These factors caused the relationship between receivables and profitability to be statistically insignificant.

REFERENCES

- Alexander., & Nobes. 2020. *Financial Accounting An International Introduction*. New York: Pearson.
- Daniel et al. 2013. A review of trade credit literature: Opportunities for research in operations. *European Journal of Operational Research* Volume 231, Issue 2, 1 December 2013, Pages 245-256. doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2013.03.016
- Dewi, Diana Setiyo. 2021. PENGARUH PERPUTARAN PIUTANG USAHA DAN PERSEDIAAN TERHADAP RETURN ON ASSET PADA PERUSAHAAN AGRIBISNIS YANG GO PUBLIK. *Jurnal Manajemen dan Bisnis*. Vol.3.01. stiejayakarta.ac.id/index.php/JMBJayakarta/article/view/81
- Garrison., Noreen., & Brewer. 2021. *Managerial Accounting Seventeenth Edition*. New York: McGraw-Hill Education.
- Hadi, Ukky Rizal Setyo., & Yusuf Ramayani. 2022. PENGARUH PERPUTARAN PIUTANG TERHADAP PROFITABILITAS PADA PERUSAHAAN OTOMOTIF (STUDI KASUS PT. ASTRA OTO PARTS, TBK PERIODE 2018-2019). *Jurnal Manajemen Terapan dan Keuangan*. Vol.11. 01. onlinejournal.unja.ac.id/mankeu/artic le/view/14825
- Hery. 2015. *Analisis Laporan Keuangan*. Yogyakarta: CAPS (Center for Academic Publishing Service).
- _____. 2017. *Kajian Riset Akuntansi*. Jakarta: Grasindo.
- _____. 2019. *Pengendalian Akuntansi & Manajemen*. Yogyakarta: Geva Media.
- Idx.co.id. 2022
- Kasmir. 2021. *Analisis Laporan Keuangan Edisi Revisi*. Depok: Rajawali Press.
- Kieso., Weygandt., dan Warfield. 2014. *Intermediate Accounting IFRS Edition Second Edition*. New York: John Wiley & Sons.
- _____. 2018. *Intermediate Accounting IFRS Edition Third Edition*. New York: John Wiley & Sons.
- _____. 2020. *Intermediate Accounting IFRS Edition Fourth Edition*. New York: John Wiley & Sons
- Munandar, Iin Setiawati., Hasyim, Sitti Hajerah., & Samsinar. 2020. PENGARUH PIUTANG TAK TERTAGIH TERHADAP PROFITABILITAS PADA PERUSAHAAN PEMBIAYAAN YANG TERDAFTAR DI BURSA EFEK INDONESIA. *Fakultas Ekonomi Universitas Negeri Makasar*. eprints.unm.ac.id/16581/1/Jurnal%20iin%20Setiawati%20Munandar1492141010.pdf
- Penyajian Laporan Keuangan. Iaiglobal.or.id, 2022
- Prastika Deilla. 2021. Pengaruh Piutang tak Tertagih, Perputaran Piutang terhadap Profitabilitas pada Perusahaan Manufaktur yang Terdaftar di BEI pada Tahun 2018- 2020. *Jurnal Ekonomi & Bisnis*: Vol.2. 2, 174-184.
- Saraswati et al. 2019. *Akuntansi Keuangan Tinjauan IFRS*. Medan: Andalan Bintang Ghonim.
- Warren., Reeve., & Duchac. 2016. *Accounting 27th Edition*. Boston: Cengage Learning.
- Yanti & Maemunah Mumun. 2020. Pengaruh Perputaran Piutang dan Perputaran Persediaan terhadap Profitabilitas (Studi Empiris pada Perusahaam Sektor Industri Barang Konsumsi yang terdaftar di BEI Periode 2015–2018). *AKUISISI JOURNAL AKUNTANSI*. Vol.16.2,3943. fe.ummetro.ac.id/ejournal/index.php/JA/article/view/448/pdf

Issued: 10.09.2025
ISBN: ' 978-625-378-300-6 '

